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The Material and Social Deprivation in Europe

Between 2015 and 2021 it decreased by 34.28%

The Eurostat calculates the value of the rate of severe material and social deprivation. The serious material and social deprivation in Europe consist in a lack of resources that is experienced by a population that experiences at least 7 out of 13 deprivations. These are people who have difficulty:

1. to pay the rent or the bills;
2. to keep the house adequately hot;
3. to incur unexpected expenses;
4. To eat meat, fish or a protein equivalent per day;
5. A week of vacation away from home;
6. to buy a car or a van for personal use;
7. Replace worn furniture;
8. Replace worn clothes with new ones;
9. Have two pairs of adequate shoes;
10. Spend a small amount of money every week for itself;
11. have regular leisure activities;
12. Being together with friends/family for a drink/meal at least once a month;
13. Have an Internet connection.

Ranking of European countries by the value of the serious material and social deprivation rate in 2021. Romania is in the first place for the value of the rate of severe material and social deprivation in 2021 with an amount of 23.1%, followed by Bulgaria with an amount 19.15 and Greece with an amount of 13.9%. In the middle of the standings there are Latvia with an amount of 5.3%, followed by Ireland with an amount of 5.1% and Germany with an amount of 4.3%. Slovenia closes the ranking with an amount of 1.8%, followed by Sweden with an amount of 1.4% and Finland with a value of 1.1%.

Ranking of European countries for the value of the percentage variation of the serious material and social deprivation rate between 2015 and 2021. Sweden is in the first place for percentage variation of the rate of severe material and social deprivation with an amount of 27.27% even to an amount of 0.30 units, followed by Spain with an amount of 12.16% equal to an amount of 0.90 units, and from Finland with an amount of 10.00% equal to a value of 0.10 units. In the middle of the standings there are the Netherlands with an amount of -34.38% equal to an amount of -1.10 units, followed by Austria with an amount of -37.93% equal to an amount of -1.10 Unit, followed by Portugal with an amount of -44.95% equal to an amount of -4.90 units. Poland closes the ranking with an amount of -62.82% equal to an amount of -4.90 units, followed by Latvia with a value of -65.58% equal to an amount of

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-10.10 units and from Cyprus with an amount of 67.09% equal to an amount of -5.30 units. On average for the countries considered the value of the percentage variation of the rate of severe material and social deprivation has decreased by -34.28% or an amount equal to -4.15 units.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. 4 Clusters are detected:

- Cluster 1: Ireland, Portugal, Belgium, Italy, Slovakia, Spain, France, Croatia, Malta;
- Cluster 2: Romania, Bulgaria;
- Cluster 3: Netherlands, Austria, Estonia, Luxembourg, Czech Republic, Finland, Sweden, Denmark, Slovenia, Germany, Poland, Cyprus;
- Cluster 4: Hungary, Greece, Lithuania, Latvia.

From the point of view of the median, the following system of the Clusters or: $C2 = 21.1 > C34 = 8.3 > C1 = 5.9 > C3 = 2$. From a strictly geographical point of view, it appears that the value of the serious material and social deprivation is very high first of all in Eastern Europe and then in southern and northern Europe.

Network analysis with the Euclidean distance. A Network Analysis is presented below with the use of the Euclidean distance. Three different network structures are identified of which two are complex and one is simplified. Specifically, there are the following connections or:

- Slovenia has a connection with the Czech Republic for an amount of 0.17 units;
- The Czech Republic has a connection with Slovenia for an amount of 0.17 units and with the Netherlands for a value equal to 0.18 units;
- The Netherlands have a connection with the Czech Republic for an amount of 0.18 units, with Estonia for an amount of 0.15 units and with Austria for an amount of 0.14 units;
- Estonia has a connection with the Netherlands equal to an amount of 0.15 units and with Austria for an amount equal to 0.15 units ;;
- Austria has a connection with the Netherlands for an amount of 0.14 units, with Estonia for a value of 0.15 units and with Denmark for an amount of 0.18 units;
- Denmark has a connection with Austria for an amount of 0.18 units.

In addition, there is a further network structure as indicated below or:

- Luxembourg has a connection with Sweden for an amount of 0.18 units and with Finland for an amount of 0.16 units;
- Finland has a connection with Luxembourg equal to an amount of 0.16 units, and with Sweden equal to an amount of 0.14 units;
- Sweden has a connection with Luxembourg equal to an amount of 0.18 units and with Finland for an amount of 0.14 units.

There is also the following simplified network structure or:

- Cyprus and Poland are connected for an amount equal to 0.17 units.

Conclusions. The serious material and social deprivation decreased between 2015 and 2021 in European countries considered to be an amount of -34.28% or an amount equal to -4.15 units. However, the situation in Romania, Bulgaria, Greece and Hungary remains very serious where the value of the serious material deprivation is respectively equal to 23.1%, 19.1%, 13.9% and 10.2%. In average about 5, 8% of the population of the countries analyzed lives a condition of serious material and social deprivation. We must consider that material deprivation is particularly serious because it

questioned the possibility of citing primary needs from a physical and social point of view and therefore reduces the chances that a person can also emancipate himself from poverty. In fact, as one of the ways to get out of poverty is known, consists in socialization and satisfaction of the primary needs that allows access to the exercise of intellectual and professional activities. The presence of economic policy interventions aimed at eliminating poverty through the growth of financial subsidies is an element necessary for the reduction of serious material deprivations.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Rank	Country	2021	Rank	Country	2021
1	Romania	23,1	15	Germany	4,3
2	Bulgaria	19,1	16	Croatia	3,5
3	Greece	13,9	17	Denmark	3,1

4	<i>Hungary</i>	10,2	18	<i>Poland</i>	2,9
5	<i>Spain</i>	8,3	19	<i>Cyprus</i>	2,6
6	<i>Lithuania</i>	6,4	20	<i>Luxembourg</i>	2,4
7	<i>Belgium</i>	6,3	21	<i>Netherlands</i>	2,1
8	<i>Portugal</i>	6	22	<i>Estonia</i>	1,9
9	<i>France</i>	5,9	23	<i>Czechia</i>	1,8
10	<i>Italy</i>	5,9	24	<i>Austria</i>	1,8
11	<i>Slovakia</i>	5,7	25	<i>Slovenia</i>	1,8
12	<i>Malta</i>	5,4	26	<i>Sweden</i>	1,4
13	<i>Latvia</i>	5,3	27	<i>Finland</i>	1,1
14	<i>Ireland</i>	5,1			